

Interdisciplinarity as an Innovation Policy in Higher Education: Definition, Drivers of Adoption, Organizational and Epistemological Challenges, and a Conceptual Framework for Managerial and Leadership Roles

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ABSTRACT: Higher education institutions around the world are one of the main drivers of the development of nations via providing an environment conducive to teaching, learning, and creative processes. These institutions are the incubators of research, development, and innovation. They are responsible for preparing and graduating qualified human cadres with the necessary knowledge, skills, competences, and attitudes. Thus, higher education in developed countries have sought to modernize their academic policies and programs, through the development and establishment of interdisciplinarity at the level of bachelor and postgraduate programs. This paper sought to explore global practices and scientific studies with respect to interdisciplinarity in higher education. It focused on understanding the role of academic and administrative leadership in planning, developing, and managing interdisciplinary programs. Studies indicate that many constituencies in higher education institutions confuse the concept of interdisciplinarity with other similar concepts. Accordingly, the paper sought to clarify the meaning of interdisciplinarity in higher education and distinguish it from other concepts based on the theory of the field. The paper then discussed the rationale and motives for adopting interdisciplinary programs in higher education. Plus, Since in-house interdisciplinary programs are a recent experience in many institutions of higher education in some developing countries, studies have indicated that there are a number of impediments hindering or, at best, making it difficult to establish, develop, plan, and manage such programs. The paper discussed these constraints and presented a framework for academic and administrative leadership roles to deal effectively with these challenges and difficulties.

Keywords: higher education; interdisciplinarity challenges; interdisciplinarity management and leadership.

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1. Introduction

Higher education is one of the main drivers in the evolution of human societies at all levels. It is the most important avenue for societies to sustain the gains of the past, strengthen the present, and envision and attain the future. Higher education is a bedrock institution contributing to the production of human capital; that is, the human resources that are being raised, socialized, and equipped to meet national needs in all areas of life and

developments: economical, industrial, agricultural, cultural, just to name a few (Goldin & Kats, 2009; Toutkoushian & Paulsen, 2016). Higher education is also one of the most important safety valves in the preservation of cultural and national identity through the promotion, conservation, and development of cultural resources (cultural capitals), through constructively critical examination (Pascarella & Terenzini, 2005; Winkle-Wagner, 2010). Plus, higher education is a key player in the economy especially in developed countries, such as United States of America and United Kingdom, not only at the national or regional level but also at the global and international level, through knowledge production and applications; which have become a product that can be invested or utilized to generate economic returns, namely called knowledge economy BIS (2016) or academic capitalism Slaughter & Rhoades (2009).

The roles of higher education institutions, both in different countries of the world as well as in Saudi Arabia, is of tremendous importance. This is due to the fact that these institutions are organic and essential to any society seeking and aspiring to leadership in numerous spheres, educationally, socially, economically, just to name a few. (Abouammoh, 2017; BIS, 2016; Godonoga & Sporn, 2023; Smith & Abouammoh, 2013; Toutkoushian & Paulsen, 2016). However, the actual and expected roles of higher education institutions have not kept pace with modern changes in various areas; therefore, these institutions face many pressures and criticisms from different quarters: society, government, profit and non-profit organizations, and enterprises etc. (Altbach et al., 2011; Moscardini, Strachan, & Vlasova, 2020; Thelin, 2022). A great number of these criticisms relates to the observed low and poor performance in the university's primary functions: teaching, research, and community service as well as the policies, regulations, and processes underlying these functions (Al-Qarawi, 2022; Alshehri, 2016; Badran, Baydoun, & Hillman, 2019; Altbach et al., 2011; Essa, 2011; Moscardini et al., 2020).

Interestingly, many higher education institutions continue to execute their main functions on the basis of deep-rooted traditional philosophy and methods associated with their establishment and history (Bess & Dee, 2008; Birnbaum, 1988; Clark, 1972; Moscardini et al., 2020), which, if not taken into account, would be a major obstacle to their flexibility and survivability to develop, renovate, and innovate in their functions, processes, policies and systems for effectively and efficiently dealing with meeting current and future requirements and demands at all levels (e.g., economic, social, and cultural). By extrapolating the findings of recent educational, administrative, and economic studies, experts and researchers in these and other sciences showed that universities face many challenges in terms of inputs, processes, internal relations, outputs, processes, and external relations (Al-Qarawi, 2022; Badran et al., 2019; Essa, 2011; Altbach et al., 2011; Moscardini et al., 2020, National Academics of Science, Engineering, & Medicine, 2018).

Among the most pronounced challenges and criticisms facing higher education institutions are the rigidity of educational philosophy, programs, and academic curricula as well as the weak alignment, responsiveness, and effectiveness in meeting modern and future social, economic and cultural needs, just to name a few (Al-Qarawi, 2022; Badran et al., 2019; Essa, 2011; Moscardini et al., 2020; National Academics of Science, Engineering,

& Medicine, 2018). Accordingly, higher education institutions in developed and some developing countries have developed, invented, and adopted a new academic philosophy and curricula with a view for meeting existing challenges, keeping pace with modern developments, and looking ahead to future requirements and aspirations. This innovative policy and approach represents what scientists and researcher called interdisciplinarity (Frodeman, Klein, & Pacheco, 2017; Leišytė, Rose, & Sterk-Zeeman, 2022), which focuses on the principle of complementarity and integration of different disciplines (Holley, 2009; Klein, 2006; Lattuca, 2001; Vienni-Baptista & Klein, 2022).

It is important to emphasize that this academic innovation has historical antecedents in higher education institutions in developed countries (Chettiparamb, 2007; Frodeman et al., 2017). However, it is considered new in many developing countries, such as Saudi Arabia, whose educational history is very short compared to industrialized countries such as the United States of America, United Kingdom, and Australia (Smith & Abouammoh, 2013). The adoption, development, and establishment of interdisciplinary academic programs in Saudi higher education institutions are very recent and require many studies and scientific discussions illustrating what they are, their benefits, and implications if implemented properly, and how they are developed, planned, and managed by those concerned at all levels in higher education institutions, such as academic leaders and faculty members.

Problem and Questions of the Study

There is a knowledge and scientific gap in Arab studies in terms of interdisciplinary academic programs. Specifically, there are very few scientific studies investigating and reviewing the possibility of adopting and implementing interdisciplinary policies and programs at Saudi universities, and how they can be developed, planned, established, and managed in line with the regulatory and institutional system in higher education institutions. There is also a lack of scientific studies that attempt to draw on the experiences of higher education institutions around the world and take advantage of their expertise with regard to the philosophy of interdisciplinarity programs, and the ways in which they are implemented, assessed, and evaluated in higher education institutions. Moreover, after consideration and scrutiny of previous studies, there is ambivalence associated with what are academic interdisciplinarity, how they are carried out and managed, and the acceptance of this innovation by institutional constituencies such as academic leaders, teaching staff, students and others. Additionally, there is a limitation in the literature in terms of managerial and leadership frameworks and models addressing interdisciplinarity in higher education. In the light of these observations, this analytical study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What is interdisciplinarity? What are the differences between interdisciplinary and disciplinarity based on the views of experts and theoreticians in this area?
2. What are some of the most important motives and drivers for adopting and implementing interdisciplinary policies and programs in higher education institutions?

3. What are some of the critical challenges (material and non-material) that hinder or weaken the adoption and implementation of interdisciplinary policies and programs in higher education institutions?
4. What are the roles of managerial and academic leaders in the adoption, development, planning, and management of interdisciplinary policies and programs? What possibilities do they have for overcoming physical and non-physical challenges and constraints?

The Significance and Objectives of the Study:

This study attempts at promoting scientific advancement with regard to interdisciplinarity in higher education via endeavoring to provide a clear picture of the interdisciplinarity nature and its benefits and the actual and expected roles of academic leaders, faculty members, and others in the adoption, development, establishment, and management of this educational innovation (Kroll & Schubert, 2023). Thus, this study seeks to provide a scoping analysis in order to achieve several objectives:

1. This study focuses on the nature, similarities, and differences of interdisciplinarity compared to other concepts associated with it. Hence, it aims at contributing to developing further knowledge of this subject among academic leaders, faculty members, and others at all levels of higher education institutions.
2. This study seeks to shed light on the most important theoretical and practical drivers and justifications for adopting and implementing interdisciplinarity in higher education institutions, thereby educating and alerting managerial and academic leaders, and faculty members as well as others of the significance of this innovation and its effectiveness in meeting current and future needs.
3. This study endeavors to identify and discuss a number of critical challenges that hinder or weaken the adoption, development, and management of interdisciplinarity in higher education institutions. Thus, it attempts at informing academic leaders and faculty members of these challenges and their effects on the institutional system both internally and externally.
4. This study aims at proposing a conceptual and procedural framework for adopting, developing, and managing interdisciplinarity in higher education institutions, and how managerial academic leaders and others can take advantage of this framework to effectively deal with actual and expected obstacles and challenges at the various organizational levels.

2. Method

There are many scientific methods classified into two broad categories: quantitative and qualitative research methodologies (Salkind, N, 2012). Given the problem of this study and its research questions, the appropriate research approach is the descriptive and analytical method of previous scientific studies. Accordingly, the study's research method falls under the umbrella of the qualitative research domain. Specifically, this study used the

scoping review method. (Munn, Peters, Stern, Tufanaru, McArthur, & Aromataris, 2018). This technique is very appropriate for such a preliminary study, as it seeks to achieve several objectives, including: surveying previous studies in general or in detail, identifying knowledge gaps in previous scholarly works, and clarifying the scientific concepts presented in previous studies (Munn et al., 2018).

It is important to note that this study reviewed and examined many research papers published in scientific journals. This study employed a number of criteria to facilitate and organize the research process. These included the following:

1. This study focused on research published in English scientific journals.
2. The study placed an emphasis on scientific papers published in two of the world's most popular research classifications: ISI and Scopus.
3. This study used a number of keywords for identifying scientific articles relevant to the questions of this study. It consisted of the following: interdisciplinarity, integrated education, interdisciplinary research, interdisciplinary teaching, and management of interdisciplinarity (managing or administering interdisciplinarity), leadership of interdisciplinarity, drivers of interdisciplinarity, barriers to interdisciplinarity, and challenges of interdisciplinarity.
4. This paper concentrated on studies published in the field of higher education. Many of the studies published in the field of general education were excluded, except when they are associated with interdisciplinarity in higher education.
5. This study gave greater and deeper focus to studies on management and leadership of interdisciplinarity in higher education, as they are the essence of this study.
6. This study capitalized on newly published scientific research in order to update research on the management and leadership of interdisciplinarity in institutions of higher education. It should be noted that some studies published in the past were cited for their theoretical and practical importance.

3. Discussion of the Findings

In this part of the paper, many studies, research, and scientific articles were analyzed in the light of the research questions. The discussion and analysis are organized according to the sequence of the content and substance of the study's questions mentioned earlier.

Definitions of Interdisciplinarity and the Similarities and Differences with Other Concepts:

Before going into the discussion of what is interdisciplinarity, its characteristics, and the distinctions between it and other similar concepts, it is necessary to begin by analyzing and discussing the concept of disciplinarity. This is due to the fact that higher education institutions in the present era require investigators of these institutions to study both

disciplinarity as well as interdisciplinarity and the similarities and differences between them. This is because much of the criticisms of disciplinarity (specialization) is based on knowledge of convergent and divergent points shared or not shared between the two concepts (Holley, 2009; Lattuca, 2001).

According to previous studies, many scholars and historians consider that the word disciplinarity (specialization) in general and in higher education in particular has historical depth. Some consider that the word surfaced with the inception of higher education institutions (Holley, 2009; Lattuca, 2001; Chettiparamb, 2007). Others contend that it has historical depth that goes back to ancient philosophy (Turner, 2017). However, what is important is that the origin of this word generally emphasizes the specialized and disciplined education provided to the recipients (Frodeman et al., 2017). Moreover, this word has evolved and took on epistemological and methodological significance in higher education institutions (Holley, 2009; Chettiparamb, 2007). Therefore, previous literature is rich with many terms denoting various connotations regarding what disciplinarity or specialization is and its characteristics; hence, there is no a single definition or term to be agreed upon.

For example, there are some perceptions that disciplinarity in higher education institutions represent types of groups that include a number of individuals with similar degrees in the same field of specialization that distinguish them from others specializing in different fields of inquiry (Becher & Trowler, 2006; Turner, 2017). These groups are organized into units with specific powers and privileges for creating and making decisions, policies, and procedures, such as the admission of persons (e.g., students and faculty members), and for granting degrees (e.g., diplomas) according to scientific, epistemological, methodological, and organizational orientations, which are recognized by internal and external constituencies (Becher & Trowler, 2006; Trowler, 2014). Doing so gives these groups credibility, confidence, and formality both at the level of their educational institution and at the level of external institutions and organizations that are targeted by these units for their material and non-material outputs. (Becher & Trowler, 2006; Chettiparamb, 2007; Holley, 2009; Lattuca, 2001). There are also some studies that suggest that specialization is an intellectual and mental structure that allows and facilitates the transfer and exchange of knowledge from an individual to another, from an individual to a group, and/or from a group to another. Some other studies perceive specialization as those homogeneous groups that are bound by common knowledge, scientific orientation and methodology as well as culture norms (Chettiparamb, 2007; Holley, 2009; Lattuca, 2001). Therefore, some researchers coined the term "academic tripe" as an indication of the impact of strong and deep specialization on the group of members not only on purely cognitive aspects but also on other aspects such as values, beliefs, and behaviors (Becher & Trowler, 2006; Trowler, 2014).

In the light of this discussion, academic discipline is a specific field of study, with an epistemological and methodological structure or composition. This field of study involves and is practiced by a community of scientists, researchers, and specialists who possess general knowledge and methodology in the field of study, and a very specialized knowledge and methodology within this discipline. Therefore, academic discipline in general can be

considered as a structural unit with recognized knowledge, methodology, procedure, and organizational boundaries that distinguish it from others, while at the same time constraining, framing, and often preventing contact, cooperation, and participation with other units in different fields even in the same institution (Becher & Trowler, 2006).

The framing and restriction associated with academic disciplines in higher education have faced numerous criticisms from within and outside higher education institutions due to organizational rigidity and closed and limited interaction with other disciplines. Consequently, academic disciplines are, to varying degrees, seen as isolated from reality at both organizational and societal levels (National Academies of Science, Engineering, & Medicine, 2018). Furthermore, academic discipline has intentionally or inadvertently exacerbate over-specialization, lack of efficiency and effectiveness in dealing with modern issues and problems, and limited capacity to keep pace with current developments and anticipate future expectations and requirements. New concepts, perceptions, and innovations have therefore emerged. They aim at overcoming many disadvantages resulting from the deep commitment to disciplinarity or specialization in higher education institutions. This innovation in higher education is called academic interdisciplinarity (Holley, 2009; Lattuca, 2001).

More recently, academic interdisciplinarity in higher education has gained a great deal of momentum. It is adopted in a growing number of higher education institutions in industrialized countries as well as in some developing countries (De Souza Marins, Ramos, Ferreira, Costa, & Costa, 2019; Donina, Seeber, & Paleari, 2017; Leišytė, Rose, & Sterk-Zeeman, 2022). It is important to note that although interdisciplinarity term is widely used in the literature and replete with various conceptualizations, there is no agreed upon definition of such concept (Frodeman et al., 2017; Madsen, 2018), and there is an argument that calling for abandoning interdisciplinarity due to its ambiguous and heterogeneous definition. However, this paper endeavors to, at least, further our understanding of this ambiguity via reporting and discussing the most important definitions and perceptions of interdisciplinarity. At the outset, it must be highlighted that interdisciplinarity consists of two words: The first is inter, and the second is discipline. What is important is the first word as it adds epistemological and methodological dimensions that emphasize the idea of integration, convergence, and amalgamation (Chettiparamb, 2007).

The concept of interdisciplinarity is more modern than that of disciplinarity, especially in higher education institutions. Previous studies show that this term dates back to the beginning of the twentieth century and was used to refer to research involving two or more professional associations, especially in purely scientific disciplines such as physics and others (Chettiparamb, 2007; Turner, 2017). Interdisciplinarity then evolves and expands to be seen as a holistic and complementary concept and frame that, through its epistemological and methodological adoption, can bring about fundamental and innovative changes and reforms to the key functions of higher education institutions: teaching, research, and community service (Holley, 2009; Lattuca, 2001). However, with these developments and changes, this concept is expanding further, and there are multiple definitions, terminologies, and classifications (Frodeman et al., 2017; Madsen, 2018).

Some studies suggest that interdisciplinarity is a metaphor of knowledge and research curricula borrowed from a particular discipline for the study of a particular issue or phenomenon located in another discipline that is difficult to understand based on existing knowledge and methodology in this discipline (De Souza Marins et al., 2019; Frodeman et al., 2017; Jacobs & Frickel, 2009). There is also definition of interdisciplinarity as the use of theoretical and procedural knowledge and research curricula from different disciplines to try to find scientific answers to issues and phenomena that fall within the boundaries of different disciplines. Additionally, there are some studies portraying interdisciplinarity as the ability to use theoretical knowledge and research curricula from different disciplines to study phenomena or issues that exist in all disciplines in order to find scientific solutions that could be applied in a particular discipline regardless of their applicability and use in other disciplines (Chettiparamb, 2007; Jacobs & Frickel, 2009). There are also other scientific terms suggesting that interdisciplinary is an attempt to obtain scientific answers using research and procedural knowledge and curricula from a variety of disciplines and their application to issues outside the scope of specialization and sometimes outside the scope of the educational institution (Frodeman et al., 2017).

These definitions focus on multiple aspects and dimensions of interdisciplinarity. They show explicit and implicit references to the features of interdisciplinarity as a complementary and integrative mechanism (Chettiparamb, 2007; Frodeman et al., 2017; Jacobs & Frickel, 2009). Nevertheless, some focus on partial interdisciplinarity as in the first definition while others focus on multidisciplinary as in the second definition. Still others highlight cross-disciplinarity as in the third definition and transdisciplinary as in the last definition. Based on the conceptualizations of scholars in this area, the perceptions, concepts, and features of interdisciplinarity are extensive, profound, and comprehensive. Accordingly, we can broadly express interdisciplinarity as a way of thinking and acting that supports and promotes in its members the concept and value of cooperation, partnership, integration and inclusiveness. It facilitates the ways and procedures for making use of and genuine integration of theoretical and procedural knowledge with research and philosophical approaches from a variety of disciplines when studying a particular phenomenon or issue, finding scientific and practical answers and solutions, and developing a new profound and comprehensive understanding of the issue or phenomenon under investigation.

In light of this, academic interdisciplinarity reflects the degree of engagement and collaboration between two or more disciplines focusing largely on a problem or subject that is present in one or multiple disciplines and promoting participatory and cooperative involvement between researchers from various disciplines. It underscores the importance of the dynamic interaction between theoretical and procedural knowledge and research curricula from different disciplines and attempts to integrate them into a new format, framework, or conceptualization facilitating greater understanding of a problem, subject, or phenomenon under study (Dallmann, 2021; National Academies of Science, Engineering, & Medicine, 2018). Hence, interdisciplinarity facilitates the development of theoretical and procedural knowledge and research curricula aiming at finding creative and innovative

solutions that would not have seen the light without the dynamic interactions and integrations between two or more disciplines and their constituencies (Frodeman et al., 2017).

Motivations and Drivers for Adopting Interdisciplinarity in Higher Education:

Given the scrutiny of previous studies and current developments and future prospects, there are a number of motives and justifications for higher education institutions to adopt and establish interdisciplinary policies (e.g., academic programs). The adoption and development of this academic and organizational innovations might be attributed to two main themes (Dallmann, 2021; Falcus, Cameron, & Halsall, 2019; Frodeman et al., 2017; Kuipers-Dirven, Janssen, & Hoekman, 2023; Holley, 2009; Lattuca, 2001; Moscardini et al., 2020; Siedlok & Hibbert, 2014; Vienni-Baptista, Fletcher, & Lyall, 2023). The first is related to the general perception of interdisciplinary programs as one of the most effective academic initiatives and policies via which numerous educational, social, economic, technical benefits and others are attained and realized within and outside the boundaries of the institution. The second emphasizes the higher education inherent roles in bringing about the necessary changes to deal with and respond effectively, productively, and efficiently to current and future challenges and requirements (Dallmann, 2021; Falcus et al., 2019; Frodeman et al., 2017; Kuipers-Dirven et al., 2023; Holley, 2009; Lattuca, 2001; Moscardini et al., 2020; Vienni-Baptista et al., 2023). The following is a brief presentation of the most important factors that have driven many institutions of higher education in industrialized and developing countries to adopt interdisciplinary policies. In a nutshell, there are five broad drivers and justifications that emphasize the importance of adopting and developing interdisciplinary policies in higher education (National Academies of Science, Engineering, & Medicine, 2018; Rhoten & Parker, 2004):

First, inherent complexity in nature and society.

This means that nature and society reside in an overall comprehensive system in which various complex systems are living, interacting, influencing each other and get affected by a great number of factors and variables that are often difficult to identify and quantify. Therefore, many natural phenomena and societal issues necessitate integration and cooperation from a variety of disciplines in order to identify sustainable scientific answers and appropriate methodological solutions through which these problems and issues can be tackled effectively and efficiently (Siedlok & Hibbert, 2014; Taylor, Jokela, Laine, Rajaniemi, Jokinen, Häikiö, & Lönnqvist, 2021; Vienni-Baptista et al., 2023). Examples of some issues and phenomena include climate and environmental changes, biodiversity loss, and recently COVID-19 pandemic.

Second, exploring basic and primary research problems existing in a variety of disciplines.

This means that there are epistemological and methodological gaps between certain disciplines, or that there are problems and issues that cannot be answered within the boundary of a discipline but through the cognitive and methodological collaboration of

diverse disciplines (Reijula, Kuorikoski, & MacLeod, 2023; Vienni-Baptista et al., 2023). In doing so, this results in many instances in the creation of new disciplines such as biochemistry and eco-economics, and cybersecurity.

Third, finding sustainable solutions to social issues.

Science has become a necessity of human life, especially at the present time, since human society depends on science as a tool and means through which existential and critical decisions are made. Therefore, interdisciplinary policy is considered a valuable and effective mechanism for decision makers, such as leaders, managers, politicians, planners, and others in various institutions, in order to deal with wicked problems (Rittel & Webber, 1973; Vienni-Baptista et al., 2023), to which it is difficult to find appropriate solutions except through the integration and collaboration of various disciplines. Some examples of social problems include poverty and social injustice.

Fourth, the increasing omnipresence and ubiquity of technologies.

Human society today, with all its institutions at all levels, is living in the crucible of the digital, technical, and industrial revolution that has evolved to what is called the Fourth Industrial Revolution (Schwab, 2017), a powerful and far-reaching revolution in every sphere of life within and outside all institutions of society, including higher education (Gleason, 2018). This has led to many positive changes, such as the emergence of technologies assisting human beings in many fields, such as medicine, communications, transportations, trade, education and others. Moreover, technological and industrial development and progress have created many challenges, such as increasing unemployment rates due to digital automation, increasing problems of property and intellectual rights, and increasing problems of cyber-attacks (Schwab, 2017). Accordingly, these issues and phenomena require a variety of disciplines to deal in a scientific way with current issues and future developments.

Fifth, the increasing need for developing and readying a holistic human personality.

The preparation of the holistic personality means that an individual should develop and have the essential knowledge, skills, and attitudes in order to take advantage and benefit from theoretical, practical, and methodological knowledge residing within different disciplines. This is for enabling such individuals to handle and solve complex issues and wicked- problems (Lockeman & Howorka, 2015; McCune, Tauritz, Boyd, Cross, Higgins, & Scoles, 2023; Power & Handley, 2019; Shandas & Brown, 2016; Turner, Cotton, Morrison, & Kneale, 2022) and be able to have the competencies for dealing with and adapting to current and future variables such as issues of employment and unemployment. Achieving this could be attained through development and implementation of curricula that focus on innovation and creativity via integration and collaboration of multiple disciplines.

Challenges Facing Interdisciplinarity in Higher Education

The following is a brief overview of the most important challenges that weaken or hinder the adoption, development, and management of interdisciplinary policies in higher education. These challenges are categorized into two main themes, which include several subthemes. The aim of this classification is to facilitate intellectual discussion. It should be noted that this classification does not neglect the importance of the dynamic interactions between the themes and subthemes and the implications and consequences associated with them (Buanes & Jentoft, 2009; Cai & Lönnqvist, 2021; Lindvig & Ulriksen, 2019; Lyall, Meagher, Bandola, & Kettle, 2015; Holley, 2009; McCoy & Gardner, 2012; Müller & Kaltenbrunner, 2019; National Academics of Science, Engineering, & Medicine, 2018; Salmela, MacLeod, & Munck af Rosenschöld, 2021; Siedlok & Hibbert, 2014; Turner et al., 2022; Vienni-Baptista et al., 2023; Wallace & Clark, 2017; Welch-Devine, Shaw, Coffield, Heynen, 2018; Ylijoki, 2022). The following are summaries of the challenges and constraints based on the aforementioned studies:

First, institutional challenges

The regulation system of higher education institutions represent one of the most powerful and profound challenges to the adoption, establishment, development, and management of interdisciplinary policies. This is because most higher education institutions in many countries around the world are based on academic departments (Gonaim, Peters, 2016; Walvoord, Carey, Smith, Soled, Way, & Zorn, 2000), and the epistemological, methodological, and procedural organization unit in these departments are linked to disciplinary or specialized academic programs (Kok & McDonald, 2017). Further, many departments are based on one or more disciplines, each of which has its own characteristics and boundaries that distinguish it from other disciplines within the same department. As a matter of fact, the boundaries between academic disciplines intensify when moving away or out of the scope and limits of the academic department, manifesting strongly its distinguishing characteristics at the school, college, and institutional levels (Buanes & Jentoft, 2009; Holley, 2009; Lattuca, 2001). There are, therefore, a number of challenges and constraints associated with the regulatory system. They are summarized below:

The organizational structure

The organizational structure of academic disciplines in many institutions of higher education reinforces the idea of isolation and minimizes - if not prevents- the interaction and collaboration between academic disciplines even in the same department (Buanes & Jentoft, 2009; Holley, 2009; Lattuca, 2001). Thus, constituencies and members of these disciplines (faculty, students, etc.) live in the silo of their specialties (Becher & Trowler, 2006). They are confined to themselves and within their department and have limited or no knowledge of developments and events taking place in other adjacent or remote disciplines. Therefore, academic specialization is a force of magnetic and physical attraction that increases the strength of specialization by attracting all components involved in the educational system within the discipline. At the same time, it strengthens the power of

exclusion and marginalization of interdisciplinary programs by making them live in the margins of academic disciplines and departments (Buanes & Jentoft, 2009; Holley, 2009; Lattuca, 2001). Consequently, this limits the harmony, consistency, and sustainability of interdisciplinary programs as key organizational components within the fabric of higher education institutions.

The organizational policies

Organizational policies at the level of institutions, colleges, and departments define the frameworks, procedures, priorities, expectations, and cognitive and behavioral standards that shape and affect disciplinarity and interdisciplinarity and their constituencies (Kuipers-Dirven et al., 2023; Vienni-Baptista et al., 2023). However, current administrative processes, such as planning and evaluation, emphasize the idea of specialization, and the majority of organizational policies support the idea of academic division and specialization rooted in the fabric of higher education institutions. Examples of these policies and regulations include procedures related to supporting research and developmental processes as well as procedures related to the processes of measuring, assessing, and evaluating the performance of consistencies within the academic departments and disciplines in terms of teaching, research, and community service (Kuipers-Dirven et al., 2023; Salmela et al., 2021; Vienni-Baptista et al., 2023). Therefore, organizational policies based on the specialized academic system limit the ability of members in any discipline to engage in interdisciplinary research, teaching, or community service because of the lack of regulatory policies supporting and legitimizing such innovation in the function of teaching, research, and community service (Welch-Devine et al., 2018).

The management and leadership

Many recent studies suggest that leadership and management in higher education institutions from the top of the organizational hierarchy to the bottom of departments and academic committees in these departments represent, to varying degrees, challenges for adopting, managing and leading interdisciplinarity. This is due to the repeated findings that academic leaders have an unclear perception and conceptualization of what the interdisciplinary policies (programs) are, how they are established, planned, developed, and managed (Cai & Lönnqvist, 2021; Lindvig, Lyall, & Meagher, 2019; Townsend, Pisapia, & Razzaq, 2015; Wowk et al., 2017). Furthermore, it is even complicated when taking into consideration past and recent studies reporting that many academic and administrative leaders lack sufficient administrative, managerial and professional preparation in order to effectively and sufficiently lead and manage higher education institutions at the various organizational units or levels (Fullan & Scott, 2009; Kezar & Eckel, 2004; Kezar, Carducci, & Contreras- McGavin, 2006).

The physical and human resources

The totality of previous research and studies indicates that the lack of material and human resources represent numerous challenges. They might hinder the establishment, development, and management of interdisciplinary programs in higher education institutions

due to their insufficiency (Müller & Kaltenbrunner, 2019; Welch-Devine et al., 2018). Examples of such resources include financial support for the development, establishment, planning, and management of interdisciplinary research, teaching, and community service, as well as the lack of adequate infrastructure and facilities that break or at least weaken organizational and environmental isolation between different disciplines and contribute to fostering interaction and collaboration between these disciplines. Another example of resources that obstruct interdisciplinary programs is the lack of a sufficient number of teaching staff with high scientific, cognitive, and methodological skills to engage in the adoption and practice of interdisciplinary programs in research, teaching, and external relations with society (Müller & Kaltenbrunner, 2019; Welch-Devine et al., 2018).

Second, Philosophical and Epistemological Barriers

The academic disciplines are distinct from each other with regard to the dominant cognitive and value system (Dominant Paradigm) (Becher & Trowler, 2006; Madsen, 2018; Trowler, 2014), which shapes and defines the philosophy of knowledge and the ensuing perceptions, frameworks, and procedures. This cognitive and value pattern greatly and deeply affect many activities and processes such as research, teaching, human interaction, upbringing, normalization, and student learning in these disciplines and their relationship with external elements of other disciplines (Lindvig & Ulriksen, 2019; Müller & Kaltenbrunner, 2019; Turner et al., 2022; Ylijoki, 2022). Therefore, the academic disciplines in their present form, organization, and status in many universities are defined and characterized by numerous determinants such as the nature of knowledge and its acquisition in these disciplines and the scientific ways to verify its credibility and facilitate its dissemination and applications in various spheres (Madsen, 2018). These determinants represent a sample of many fundamental characteristics of academic disciplines in higher education institutions emphasizing specialization, isolation, and living in the silos or ivory towers of specialties (Latatuca, 2001; Holley, 2009; Troutner, 2014; Truran, 2013). Accordingly, this reinforces particular patterns and areas of research, teaching, and community service (Lindvig & Ulriksen, 2019; Kuipers-Dirven et al., 2023). Based on previous observations and points, philosophy, knowledge, and procedural approaches will be among the most profound and powerful challenges or obstacles to interdisciplinary policy, for a number of reasons including the following:

Different perceptions of and orientation toward knowledge, facts, and science and how to acquire them and verify their credibility within academic disciplines

On the one hand, purely scientific disciplines such as mathematics, physics, biology and others view knowledge in general and scientific facts in particular as existential truths in the universe and do not change in nature due to social, psychological, economic factors, just to name a few (Becher & Troutner, 2006; Creswell, 2014; Madsen, 2018; Müller & Kaltenbrunner, 2019; Troler, 2014; Truran, 2013). Hence, scientific knowledge is consistent across the natural order regardless of the aforementioned variables and only requires educated persons (scientists) to discover it through scientific methods based on theories and assumptions that are verified and established through research and experimental

methods. Accordingly, these types of disciplines have a cognitive and scientific stability and consistency in terms of research and teaching methodologies and knowledge production and generation. On the other hand, there are social and professional disciplines such as sociology, psychology, management science and history, which view knowledge in general and facts and science in particular as different in social, psychological, cultural, educational and other fields. Therefore, these disciplines are implicitly and explicitly clinging to the notion of diversity. These and other disciplines have the momentum, complexity and depth of knowledge demonstrate that knowledge and science in these disciplines have different meanings, dimensions, and aspects, depending on many factors (social, economic, historical, educational, cultural, etc.). Thus, it is difficult to verify knowledge credibility and stability by using research and experimental methods described by some thinkers and scientists in purely academic disciplines but rather instead via using research and scientific methods suitable for these disciplines (Becher & Trowler, 2006; Creswell, 2014; Müller & Kaltenbrunner, 2019; Trowler, 2014; Truran, 2013). Accordingly, these types of disciplines lack, to varying degrees, cognitive and scientific knowledge stability in terms of research and teaching methodologies and knowledge production and generation.

Distinct usages of language, patterns of thinking, discourses, and interaction

The philosophical, cognitive, scientific and methodological differences between academic disciplines will result in differences in language usages and semantic connotations from one discipline to another. Therefore, the writing, discourses, and interaction will be rooted in the context of different disciplines and thus reflect the knowledge, values, and methodology of these disciplines, which are often complex and only meaningful and understandable to members and constituencies of these disciplines. Evidently, this situation gets more complicated when we compare purely scientific disciplines (e.g. mathematics and physics) to social and professional disciplines (e.g. education and political science) and to applied disciplines (e.g. computer science and engineering). It can even be said that different language's uses in various disciplines will, together with other factors and variables, lead to different patterns and ways of thinking that demarcate the boundaries of these disciplines and distinguish them from others (Becher & Trowler, 2006; Lindvig & Ulriksen, 2019; Trowler, 2014; Truran, 2013).

Roles of academic and administrative leadership in the developing, planning and establishing interdisciplinary programs and policies

Current and future national and global developments require highly dynamic higher education that have the capacity for interacting and adapting to current realities as well as responding and anticipating future developments. We are now living in an era of knowledge explosion, rapid digital advancements in all areas, global cultural openness, and economic, and political challenges. Higher education will therefore play a pivotal role in taking advantage of positive changes and in meeting current and future challenges by developing and promoting education that produces qualified human cadres with the necessary knowledge, values, and skills that meet present and future needs. Therefore, academic and administrative leaders in higher education institutions are primarily responsible for being

cognizant of global, regional, and local happenings with regard to the development of higher education systems. In so doing, these leaders need to adopt, effect, and lead changes in their institutions via creating and establishing innovative changes required to improve and develop the roles of the institutions and at the same time enhance their efficiency, productivity, and effectiveness.

Scientific studies, which are consulted and reviewed in this study, suggest that academic leaders and administrators are among the most important factors that facilitate, promote, and support the adoption, development, planning, establishment, and management of interdisciplinary programs and policies in higher education institutions (Cai, & Lönnqvist, 2021; Feller, 2007; Hannon, Hocking, Legge, & Lugg, 2018; Holley, 2017; Kroll & Schubert, 2023; Lindvig et al., 2019; Lyall et al., 2015; Moscardini et al., 2020; Shandas & Brown, 2016; Townsend et al., 2015; Welch-Devine et al., 2018; Wowk et al., 2017). Thus, this part of the study provides a conceptual model that aims at enabling academic and administrative leaders to deal scientifically and professionally with the challenges and constraints hindering interdisciplinary policies and programs in higher education institutions. It attempts to propose solutions that might help overcome these challenges and constraints or at least reduce their negative impacts.

It should be noted that specialists in the study of interdisciplinarity are almost unanimous that there is no single agreed-upon model or framework for the development, planning, management and establishment of interdisciplinary policies and programs in educational institutions (Jacobs, & Frickel, 2009; Leišytė et al., 2022; Wowk et al., 2017; Vienni-Baptista & Klein, 2022;). Therefore, an investigator of this issue in administrative, leadership, institutional, and social sciences and studies finds a great deal of conceptual and procedural frameworks and models that, to varying degrees, conceptualize and analyze interdisciplinarity in higher education settings and how to develop, plan, manage and establish it. On the basis of this fundamental observation, this paper attempts to draw upon these theoretical and procedural frameworks and models and identify appropriate strategies and mechanisms for establishing and managing interdisciplinary policies and programs in higher education institutions. It is worth noting that the paper's research orientation and discussion represent an interdisciplinary approach that acknowledge the complementarity and interdependency of the multiple frameworks in the study of phenomena, issues, attitudes, situations and behaviors in institutions, which many researchers and specialists in these sciences call upon (Bolman & Deal, 2017; Fullan & Scott, 2009; Gallos & Bolman, 2021; Kezar & Eckel, 2004; Kezar et al., 2006; Feller, 2007; Franks, Dale, Hindmarsh, Fellows, Buckridge, & Cybinski, 2007; Goldfien & Badway, 2015; Lattuca, 2001; Holley, 2017; Holley, 2009; Vienni-Baptista & Klein, 2022).

Many of the challenges and constraints discussed in the previous section can be analyzed and explained by using the theoretical framework developed by Scott (2013). He contends that any institution, organization, or organizational unit might be analyzed through three broad elements: the regulative element, the cognitive element, and the normative element. First, the regulative element identifies many organizational components, such as organizational structure, policies and regulations, methods of performance assessment,

evaluation, and promotion, and the relationship and interdependence of organizational units. Second, the cognitive element is concerned with mental models, knowledge, and perceptive aspects and dimensions such as goals and objectives, principles of action, priorities, and classifications and what is the internal and external reality of the institution. The normative element focuses on the presentation and development of a set of criteria and values that clarify the role of members and how to exercise their competencies and expertise and deal with other constituencies (Scott, 2013).

Employing this institutional theoretical framework, we can classify the challenges and obstacles that face and will face interdisciplinarity in higher education institutions. This classification might begin from the academic department as the smallest organizational unit to higher administration as the highest organizational unit or the institution as a whole. The contemplator on the challenges facing interdisciplinarity -the most important of which were previously mentioned- finds them reflecting and falling into the institutional conceptual framework presented by Scott (2013). While most of the organizational challenges and obstacles fall largely under the scope of the organizational element, most of the philosophical and epistemological challenges and impediments are distributed between the cognitive and normative elements. Based on this classification of challenges and constraints related to interdisciplinary policies and programs, academic and managerial leaders and other consistencies will be able to develop one or more mental models tackling and addressing these issues hinder interdisciplinarity at the institutional and organizational units (Hannon et al., 2018; Goldfien & Badway, 2015; Kezar et al., 2006). It is, therefore, expected that academic and administrative leaders will secure greater clarity and awareness of what they have to do organizationally and institutionally for adopting, developing, planning, establishing, and managing interdisciplinary policies and programs in their institutions.

Furthermore, to assist academic and managerial leaders to fulfill their required and expected roles, they might utilize and benefit from the leadership and management models developed by Bolman and Deal (2017) as well as Ballos and Bolman (2021). These scholars have clarified managerial and leadership frameworks that contend to increase the efficiency, effectiveness, and productivity of leaders and administrators in many institutions and organizations, including academic institutions. These frameworks highlight four dimensions: structural, human, political, and symbolic. The structure frame refers to policies, regulations, procedures, and organizational and hierarchical roles and positions that ultimately aim at achieving the institutional mission and strategic goals. The human frame relates to the availability of human resources, how they are recruited and socialized, their adequacy and capacity, and the provision of necessary and outgoing professional training and development. The political frame underscores the negotiation of political and organizational agendas, power, and interests of consistencies taking place within and outside the organization and the resulting conflicts, debates, and arguments about human and non-human resources and issues. Last but not least, the symbolic frame highlights the linguistic, social, and historical symbols, stories, rituals, and ceremonies within as well as

outside the organization that would directly and indirectly affect the activities, actions, and expectations in and of the organization (Bolman & Deal, 2017; Gallos & Bolman, 2021).

Accordingly, academic and administrative leaders in higher education institutions may use and benefit from the four dimensions or frames of reference (Bolman & Deal, 2017; Gallos & Bolman, 2021) in understanding and addressing the challenges in adopting, developing, planning, establishing, and managing interdisciplinarity in higher education. The following is a description of some strategies and mechanisms that might facilitate the implementation of interdisciplinary policy or program in the light of the challenges mentioned and discussed earlier:

Based on the structural (organizational) frame, building interdisciplinary policy or program in a higher education institution requires many elements. For example, it necessitates reformulation of regulatory policies in terms of loads and expectations regarding teaching, research, and community service (e.g. acknowledging the enormous teaching load and effort of interdisciplinary courses or programs compared to disciplinary courses or programs and developing policies and regulations supporting financially interdisciplinary research as well as academic promotion procedures) (Hannon et al., 2018; Müller & Kaltenbrunner, 2019). Another example is establishing proper official spaces (e.g., interdisciplinary institute or center directly linked to senior management or deanship of scientific research and graduate studies and courses or programs crossing the boundary between disciplines overseen by specific department(s)) (Hellström, Brattström, & Jabrane, 2018; Leišytė et al., 2022; McCoy & Gardner, 2012; Valles, Lucie, Montgomery, Simmons, Sweeder, & Zeleke, 2016; Vereijken, Akkerman, te Pas, van der Tuin, & Kluijtmans, 2022). In doing so, academic and managerial leaders will be more likely to facilitate and promote participation in interdisciplinary activities, whether in teaching, research, and/or community service. De facto, providing the essential infrastructure, in its various forms and types, is more likely to promote and increase the opportunity for cooperation, interaction, and fertilization between academic departments as well as institutional internal and external constituencies.

Grounded in the political frame, it is necessary to reduce the blocs in academic disciplines in terms of the various conflicts, quarrels, and arguments between members of the disciplines regarding resources (financial, human, students, and faculty members) and the extent of the usefulness, efficiency, of effectiveness interdisciplinarity (Müller & Kaltenbrunner, 2019). These tensions might be tackled productivity through diverse ways. For instance, referring to interdisciplinarity in the university's mission and strategic goals is essential (Feller, 2007; Kezar & Elrod, 2012; Welch-Devine et al., 2018). This will give the interdisciplinarity political and organizational momentums and tractions inside and outside the institution. Another example relates to the importance of involving academic leaders, such as deans and department heads as well as grassroots leaders of faculty members, in the planning and decision-making processes regarding assessment and evaluation collective and individual performance in interdisciplinary teaching, research, and community service (Goldfien & Badway, 2015; Valles et al., 2016). Still another example stresses the significance of continuous communication between academic departments and

organizational units at the university. This might be done via many ways, such as awareness-raising and orientation activities and academic and professional seminars that support and clarify the nature and necessity of interdisciplinary policies and programs and the extent of their responsiveness in meeting current and future needs. Finally yet importantly, setting a pragmatic framework that shows how to develop interdisciplinary courses and/or programs hand in hand with existing disciplines while taking into consideration the epistemological and methodological differences (McCoy & Gardner, 2012; Vereijken et al., 2022).

Based on human resources' frame, it is necessary to provide the essential human resources to carry out and on interdisciplinary tasks, works, and activities in the domain of teaching, research, and community service. Therefore, it is of paramount importance to attract faculty members who have interdisciplinary experiences in teaching and research, and who also possess dispositions and display competencies for developing interdisciplinary policies be they programs, curricula, and/or courses. The academic and managerial leader might begin enlisting faculty members interested in interdisciplinarity. Doing so will help academic and managerial leaders to establish a sustaining academic environment for interdisciplinary faculty members that secure the material, moral, and professional supports in order to carry out their interdisciplinary activities and works in teaching, research, and community services (Freiband et al., 2022; Lindvig & Ulriksen, 2019; Kroll & Schubert, 2023). In addition, establishing a supportive academic environment for faculty interested in interdisciplinarity will surely contribute to the creation of communities of practices (Pharo, Davison, McGregor, Warr, & Brown, 2014) that enhance collaboration, cooperation, interaction, and partnership between the institution's diverse constituencies to participate and partake in ideas and knowledge generations and problem solving approaches.

Through the symbolic frame, academic and managerial leaders can take a number of strategies for enhancing values, rituals, and attractive stories that demonstrate and disseminate the nature, importance, goals, relevance, and benefits of interdisciplinarity in teaching, research, and community service. They might convene and host speakers and experts in interdisciplinarity from inside and outside the university at the local, national, regional and global levels (Freiband et al., 2022). They might also celebrate any progress that occurs in adopting, developing, planning, and managing interdisciplinarity in teaching and research operations as well as community service. Last but not least, interdisciplinarity can be enhanced through the continuous dissemination of print and digital publications.

4. Conclusion

Interdisciplinarity is an academic innovation that can be applied and benefited from in higher education institutions in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and regional and Arab countries. This will enable such institutions to responsively and effectively confront current challenges and anticipate future expectations and transformations through the vital and transformative power of this innovation if adopted, implemented, and established

appropriately in the major functions of the university: teaching, research, and community service. In nutshell, this paper analyzed and explored the nature of interdisciplinarity and disciplinarity in higher education. It discussed the similarity and differences as well as the interconnectedness between these concepts. Some of the most important justifications and drivers of adopting and developing interdisciplinarity in higher education institutions were also discussed. Subsequently, the paper shed some light on some of the most important organizational and epistemological challenges and obstacles facing the adoption, development, planning, and establishment of interdisciplinarity in higher education. It then moved on to propose a managerial and leadership framework for how to develop and adopt interdisciplinarity in higher education institutions and employ appropriate and effective strategies, mechanisms and solutions to tackle organizational and epistemological barriers.

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